

Research

Performance evaluation of short-day onion (*Allium cepa* L.) germplasm

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Abstract: A field experiment was conducted at Spices Research Sub-Centre (SRSC), Bangladesh Agricultural Research Institute (BARI), Faridpur, Bangladesh during 2019-2020 to find out promising onion line/s. Twenty-five onion germplasm with BARI Piaz-1 and BARI Piaz-4 (as check) were evaluated in a randomized complete block design in the trial. The results revealed that onion lines/varieties studied differed significantly on yield attributes, yield and quality of onion. The genotype AC Bog 413 had superior performance in incidence of bolting (2.36%), disease severity (13.66%), bulb diameter (BD-4.98 cm), individual bulb weight (IBW-36.76 g), multiplier bulb (0.22%), days to maturity (103.33 days) and yield (25.37 t/ha) over the recommended varieties-BARI Piaz-1 and BARI Piaz-4. The AC Bog 413 gave 66.33 & 22.57% higher IBW, 72.70 & 27.04% higher bulb yield, 98.33 & 98.29% lower split bulb and 90.74 & 91.03% lower bolting than those of BARI Piaz-1 and BARI Piaz-4, respectively. The AC Bog 413 matched with the disease severity category 2 while BARI Piaz-1 and BARI Piaz-4 matched with the category 4 under 0-5 scale. However, the BARI Piaz-1 had higher dry matter (DM) content (17.32%), higher TSS content (18.00 °brix) and stronger pungency (5.00) than those of AC Bog 413 (15.53%, 14.50 °brix, & 4.00), respectively. The values of DM content, TSS content and pungency score for BARI Piaz-4 were 15.66%, 14.59 °brix and 4.00, respectively. Simultaneously BARI Piaz-1 and AC Bog 413 exhibited firmer bulbs (9.00) than that of BARI Piaz-4 (8.25) under 0-9 scale. The skin and flesh colour of bulbs were identified as bronze red & white for BARI Piaz-1; red & white for BARI Piaz-4 and pink red & reddish for AC Bog 413, respectively. The variety BARI Piaz-4 and AC Bog 413 showed torpedo shape of bulb while BARI Piaz-1 showed flat shape of bulb. The AC Bog 413 showed the lowest storage loss (29.94%) among the genotypes/varieties followed by BARI Piaz-1 (35.53%), AC Bog 435 (36.09%) and BARI Piaz-4 (37.38%). The genotypes AC Bog 426 and AC Bog 430 also exhibited good performance in bolting (16.90, 19.75%), split bulb (15.66, 10.75%), disease rating (33.33, 19.66%), BD (4.01, 4.00 cm), IBW (28.66, 28.43 g), DM content of bulb (18.66, 19.69%), days to maturity (112.33, 99.33 days), yield (19.42, 19.39 t/ha), shape (flat, flat), firmness (9.00, 9.00), skin colour (bronze, bronze) and flesh colour (white, white), respectively. Finally, the genotypes AC Bog 413, AC Bog 426 and AC Bog 430 were found to be promising line/s to the recommended onion varieties (BARI Piaz-1/BARI Piaz-4) in most characters measured.

Keywords: Onion (*Allium cepa* L.), short-day, genotypes, varieties, evaluation, yield and quality

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Introduction

Germplasm, specially plant genetic resources for food and agriculture, are the living material used by local communities, researchers and breeders to adapt food and agricultural production to changing needs [1]. It is the basic indispensable ingredient of all breeding programs. Diversity in plant genetic resources (PGR) offers plant breeders the opportunity to develop novel and better cultivars with desirable characteristics, which include both farmer-preferred traits (yield potential and large seed etc.) and breeder-preferred traits (pest, resistance & photosensitivity), as noted by Govindaraj *et al.* (2015)[2]. The conservation of germplasm is necessary for some important reasons: maintain genetic diversity, study local genetic material and under-utilized species and to choose species suited to develop varieties [3]. No country in the world is self-sufficient in germplasm to fulfill its food requirements. Many countries heavily depend on non-indigenous crops and imported germplasm for food and agricultural development [4]. Today, all countries and all regions have become highly interdependent [5]. Improvement in yield and quality is normally achieved by selecting genotypes with desirable character combinations existing in nature or by hybridization. In Bangladesh, onion is produced 17.38 lakh metric tonnes per annum and the yield is very low, being 9.71 t/ha [6] as compared to Indian onion yield, being 16.10 t/ha [7]. So far six onion varieties have been developed by Spices Research Centre, Bangladesh Agricultural Research Institute, Bogura for cultivation in two seasons. The low productivity of onion in the country than world average and neighboring countries is led by many lacking factors in the variety like low yield, inferior quality such as splitting bulb, pre-mature bolting, poor bulb firmness, prone to disease and pest, lower shelf life, lower dry matter and total soluble solid content of bulb, lack of hybrid variety etc. Currently farmers over the country are losing their interest on BARI Piaz-1 day by day due to its lower yield and quality (specillay pre-mature bolting, splitting bulb, prone to disease & pest etc.) performance. The present production of onion is quite lower which does not meet domestic requirement. It is estimated that the country faces shortage of around 8-10 lakh metric tonnes onions per year. So, introduction, testing and selection of germplasm are the best options for getting higher yield and quality based new open pollinated varieties to meet increasing domestic demand.

The present research work was, therefore, carried out for identifying the promising open pollinated onion line/s prone to be higher yield and quality from 25 germplasm studied.

Materials and Methods

The seeds of 25 onion germplasm were collected from local and abroad sources in 2019. All genotypes (25 accession lines) and two varieties (BARI Piaz-1 and BARI Piaz-2, as check) were evaluated at the experimental field of SRSC, BARI, Faridpur, Bangladesh during 2019-2020. The experiment was placed down under a randomized complete block design with three replications to select promising onion line/s suited for high yield and quality. The onion lines studied were: AC Bog 409, AC Bog 410, AC Bog 411, AC Bog 412, AC Bog 413, AC Bog 414, AC Bog 415, AC Bog 416, AC Bog 417, AC Bog 419, AC Bog 420, AC Bog 421, AC Bog 422, AC Bog 423, AC Bog 424, AC Bog 425, AC Bog 426, AC Bog 427, AC

Bog 428, AC Bog 429, AC Bog 430, AC Bog 431, AC Bog 433, AC Bog 434 and AC Bog 435. The seeds of 27 accession lines/varieties were sown on 08 November 2019. Each of 27 entries was allotted randomly in the plot in each block. The 40-day old uniform and healthy seedlings were transplanted on 18 December 2020 in the experimental plots maintaining 15 cm x 10 cm spacing. The plot size was 3.00 m x 2.00 m which was calculated in 0.0006 ha. The experimental field was fertilized with 5 tones well-decomposed cowdung, 120 kg N, 50 kg P, 85 kg K and 40 kg S per hectare. Nitrogen, phosphate, potash and sulphur were supplied in the form of Urea, TSP, MP and Gypsum, respectively. The entire quantity of cowdung, P, K, S and one third of N were applied as basal dose during land preparation. The remaining N was used as top dress in two equal splits at 20 and 30 days after seedlings transplanting. The fungicide mancozeb/iprodione @ 3 g/litre of water was sprayed at fortnightly interval commencing from one month after transplanting of seedlings. All other recommended management practices were followed for each accession and variety. The experimental site is belonging to Agro Ecological Zone (AEZ) no. 12 (Low Ganges River Floodplain). The geographic coordinates of the trial site are 23° 11' N and 89° 09' E. While its elevation is about 12 meters above sea level. Among the crops grown in the area, onion is predominantly cultivated as irrigated crop. Soil samples were randomly collected at 0-30 cm soil depth for physical and chemical analysis before the commencement of the experiment. The physico-chemical properties of the field experimental plot are summarized in the Table 1. While monthly average air temperature, average relative humidity and total rainfall for the trial location during 2019-2020 are illustrated in Figure 1.

The data recorded were: plant height (cm), number of leaves per plant (no.), neck size (cm), percent pre-mature bolting (%), disease and thrips infestation (0-5 scale), days to maturity (days), diameter of bulb (cm), individual bulb weight (g), percent multiplier (split) bulbs (%), dry matter of bulbs (%), total soluble solid (°brix), bulbs weight per plot (kg/ha) then calculated as yield per hectare (t), shape index & shape of bulbs, bulb firmness, skin & flesh colour of bulbs, pungency and shelf life of onion. Ten plants were randomly selected from each plot for data recording and averaging it. Plant height and number of leaves were recorded at 30 and 60 days after seedling transplanting. But average plant height and number of leaves were presented in the paper. The number of bolting plants was visually counted in each plot, recorded and expressed in percent in relation to the total number of plants. Bulbs were harvested at maturity when the pseudostem becomes flaccid and unable to support the leaf blades [8]. Onions of different genotypes/varieties were harvested on several days as per maturity symptoms. Days to maturity were recorded considering days between transplanting of seedlings and harvesting of bulbs. The leaves of harvested onion were removed at seven days after curing by cutting 8-10 cm above the bulb [9]. After curing, the total bulb fresh weight was measured for each plot. The number of multiplier bulbs was visually counted in each plot, recorded and expressed in percent in relation to the total number of bulbs per plot. The percent dry matter content of bulbs was calculated by dry weight basis as per procedure of Walle *et al.* (2018) [10]. The total soluble solids (TSS) content of bulbs were recorded by hand refractometer (ATAGO, Master-53M, Japan) with a range of 0-53 °brix. The disease (purple blotch & leaf blight) severity of onion was scored by following 0-5 scale, as described by Sharma (1986) [11]. The details of scales are as follows: 0-no disease symptoms, 1- a few spots towards tip covering 10% leaf area, 2- several dark purplish brown patch covering up to 20% leaf area, 3- several patches with paler outer zone covering up to 40% leaf area, 4- leaf streaks covering up to 75% leaf area or breaking of the leaves from centre and 5- complete drying of the leaves or breaking of the leaves from the centre. Likewise, thrips infestation was also rated by following 0-5 scale. Observations were made at the first appearance of disease symptoms/thrips on plants, till the harvest at weekly intervals. Shape index of bulb is the ratio of bulb height (polar diameter) to equatorial diameter [12]. Polar diameter is the distance between the onion crown and the point of root attachment the onion. Equatorial diameter is the maximum width of the onion in plane perpendicular to the polar diameter. Henceforth, shape of bulb was assessed by using the bulb shape index. Where, shape index smaller than 1 (<1) indicates flat; shape index equal to 1 indicates globular and shape index greater than 1 (>1) indicates torpedo. Bulb firmness rating was measured in subjective method by squeezing the bulbs at different points with the hand of testers

repeatedly [12]. Before measuring bulb firmness, dry scales of bulb were removed. Firmness was rated on a scale from 1 to 9, with 1 being the softest or that giving least resistance to squeezing and 9 being the hardest, most firm bulb [13]. Skin and flesh colour of bulbs were identified by visual assessment method. Pungency of onion was evaluated with sensory/flavour perception (organoleptic taste) by a taste panel [14]. A rating scale for pungency was used, where 1 = extremely mild, 2 = mild, 3 = slightly pungent, 4 = pungent and 5 = extremely pungent. The panel was instructed to taste all of the scales (inner, middle & outer) for each sample and to clear their palates with water and apple between samples. The taste test was conducted in three days for three replications. The shelf life was recorded as the percent storage loss of onion up to October 2020. The bolting, disease, thrips, multiplier bulb, pungency and storage performance are presented graphically (Fig. 2 to 7). However, the outcomes of the other parameters are shown in Tables (Table 2 to 3).

Table 1. Physico-chemical properties of initial soil at the experimental plot of SRSC, BARI, Faridpur in 2019-2020

Soil texture	Soil pH	OM (%)	K	Ca	Mg	Total N (%)	P	S	B	Zn	Fe	Cu	Mn
			meq/100 g				µg/g soil						
Clay loam	7.89	1.92	0.41	11.93	3.65	0.12	14.25	10.74	0.28	1.29	29.95	3.05	14.86
Critical level			0.12	2.0	0.5	0.12	7.0	10.0	0.2	0.6	4.0	0.2	1.0

The recorded data were analyzed statistically as suggested by Gomez and Gomez (1984) and the means were compared by Duncan’s Multiple Range Test (DMRT) and least significant difference (LSD) for the traits of tabular & graphical presentation, respectively [15].

Results and Discussion

The genotypes/varieties used in the study exhibited a wide range of parameters measured.

Plant height

The data in Table 2 depicted that plant height was significantly influenced by genotypes/varieties studied. Mean plant height ranged from 62.13 to 48.28 cm. The tallest plant height was noticed from the AC Bog 411 followed by AC Bog 419 (60.60 cm), AC Bog 413 (60.45 cm), AC Bog 433 (60.41 cm) and AC Bog 409 (59.98 cm). The shortest plant height was registered from the AC Bog 426. However, the varieties-BARI Piaz-1 and BARI Piaz-4 produced plant of 49.99 cm and 54.05 cm, respectively. The differences among the genotypes/varieties might be due to genetic causes. The similar finding in onion was also reported by Sirajo and Namu (2019) [16] and Walle *et al.* (2018) [10]. Tesfay *et al.* (2011) opined that plant height was also governed by environmental factors especially temperature and photoperiod [17].

Number of leaves

Analysis of variance revealed significant difference on number of leaves per plant among genotypes/varieties (Table 2). Number of leaves per plant ranged from 8.85 to 7.60. The highest number of leaves per plant was observed in AC Bog 413 insignificantly followed by AC Bog 429 (8.83), AC Bog 420 (8.82), AC Bog 428 (8.81) and AC Bog 410 (8.80). While the lowest number of leaves per plant was noted in AC Bog 423. Furthermore, the values of this parameter for BARI Piaz-1 (8.01) and BARI Piaz-4 (8.32) were statistically equal to each other. The variation in number of leaves among the germplasm/varieties might happen due to difference in genetic makeup of the genotypes/varieties. The result is in consent with the finding of Ratan *et al.* (2017) [7]. The present result is on the contrary to the finding of Sirajo and Namu (2019) [16]. They stated that differences in mean number of leaves per plant among the genotypes were not significant. Number of leaves in onion is also influenced by environment, as described by Ijoyah *et al.* (2008) [18].

Neck size

The neck size was varied significantly by germplasm/varieties, narrated in the Table 2. The thickest neck diameter (1.35 cm) was observed in AC Bog 420 followed by the germplasm- AC Bog 417 (1.32 cm), AC Bog 409 (1.31 cm) and AC Bog 428 (1.30 cm). Whilst the thinnest (1.01 cm) was attained in two accession numbers- the AC Bog 413 and AC Bog 431.

Table 2. The yield, yield contributing characters and quality of onion as influenced by onion accession lines/varieties at SRSC, BARI, Faridpur during 2019-2020

Accession lines/varieties	Plant height (cm)	Neck size (cm)	No. leaves/plant	Bulb diameter (cm)	Individual bulb weight (g)
AC Bog 409	59.98a-d	1.31ab	8.20d-g	4.10b	30.17bc
AC Bog 410	59.14b-d	1.26a-g	8.80ab	4.00b	29.13b-f
AC Bog 411	62.13a	1.19e-h	8.73a-c	3.86c	27.53e-h
AC Bog 412	55.71e-g	1.29a-d	8.20d-g	3.88c	27.84d-g
AC Bog 413	60.45a-c	1.01l	8.85a	4.98a	36.76a
AC Bog 414	53.80f-h	1.28a-e	8.40a-e	3.86c	27.49e-i
AC Bog 415	56.08ef	1.21c-h	8.10e-h	4.25b	30.44b
AC Bog 416	58.14b-e	1.18f-i	7.93f-i	4.07b	29.95b-d
AC Bog 417	59.43a-d	1.32a	7.86g-i	4.01b	29.37b-e
AC Bog 419	60.60ab	1.20d-e	8.00e-i	3.85c	27.16e-i
AC Bog 420	59.71a-d	1.35a	8.82a	4.09b	30.23b
AC Bog 421	53.06g-i	1.05l	7.66hi	3.48d	20.92l

AC Bog 422	49.10k	1.09i-l	8.10e-h	3.81c	26.33g-i
AC Bog 423	50.92i-k	1.02l	7.60i	3.66d	23.93jk
AC Bog 424	57.68c-e	1.17g-j	8.20d-g	3.93c	27.99c-g
AC Bog 425	52.69h-j	1.08j-l	8.40a-e	3.41d	20.57lm
AC Bog 426	48.28k	1.19e-h	8.33c-f	4.01b	28.66b-f
AC Bog 427	55.36e-h	1.23b-h	8.40a-e	3.83c	26.96f-i
AC Bog 428	57.39de	1.30a-c	8.81ab	4.13b	29.92b-d
AC Bog 429	58.96b-d	1.27a-f	8.83a	3.90c	27.85d-g
AC Bog 430	50.70i-k	1.06kl	7.86g-i	4.000b	28.43b-f
AC Bog 431	49.32k	1.01l	8.60a-d	3.26e	18.80mn
AC Bog 433	60.41a-c	1.23b-h	7.86g-i	3.80c	25.53h-j
AC Bog 434	56.10ef	1.26a-g	8.40a-e	3.78c	25.39h-j
AC Bog 435	50.26jk	1.16f-h	8.36b-f	3.89c	27.88d-g
BARI Piaz-1	49.99jk	1.15h-k	8.01e-i	3.53d	22.10kl
BARI Piaz-4	54.05f-h	1.24c-h	8.32c-f	4.09b	29.99b-d
CV (%)	11.05	13.66	15.38	17.53	5.14
Level of sig.	**	**	**	**	**

** Significant at 1% level of probability

The neck size values for BARI Piaz-1 and BARI Piaz-4 were 1.15 cm and 1.24 cm, respectively. It is hypothesized that the variation in neck size among germplasm/varieties might be attributed to their genetic factor. The present finding is in accordance with that of Gautam *et al.* (2019) [19], Sirajo and Namu (2019) [16] and Arya *et al.* (2017) [20]. According to Sirajo and Namu (2019) [16], neck thickness is believed to influence the storability of onion with better storability from the thinner neck size.

Pre-mature bolting

The genotypes/varieties exhibited a wide range of variation on the incidence of bolting, illustrated in the Figure 2. The highest incidence of bolting (27.00%) was recorded from the genotype AC Bog 435 insignificantly followed by the variety BARI Piaz -4 (26.33%), BARI Piaz -1 (25.50%) and AC Bog 431 (24.00%). The lowest incidence of bolting (2.36%) was resulted from AC Bog 413. In addition, the genotype AC Bog 413 bolted 91.03% and 90.74% lower than that of BARI Piaz-4 and BARI Piaz-1, respectively. Abu-Rayyan and Abu-Irmaileh (2004) reported that onion required cool weather during inflorescence initiation and seed stalk development [21]. All genotypes/varieties studied were grown in a same environment. So, this difference in bolting percent could be due to hereditary causes of genotypes/varieties. This result corroborates the earlier finding of Lancaster *et al.* (1995) [22].

Contd. Table 2.

Accession lines/varieties	TSS (°brix)	Bulb dry matter (%)	Days to maturity (days)	Yield (t/ha)
AC Bog 409	15.00b-h	12.90gh	106.44a	20.09b-d
AC Bog 410	12.66h-k	14.49ef	113.33a	19.51b-f
AC Bog 411	15.00b-h	14.02fg	112.40a	18.33c-h
AC Bog 412	11.00jk	11.83hi	105.65a	18.58b-g
AC Bog 413	14.50e-h	15.53de	103.33a	25.37a
AC Bog 414	12.00i-k	12.17h	107.33a	18.30c-h

AC Bog 415	14.70c-h	19.16a	107.88a	21.17b
AC Bog 416	14.83b-h	13.22f-h	106.00a	19.94b-d
AC Bog 417	15.33b-g	11.76hi	108.33a	19.58b-e
AC Bog 419	13.65g-i	10.66i	104.00a	18.08d-h
AC Bog 420	14.40e-h	13.21f-h	103.08a	19.98b-d
AC Bog 421	16.66a-e	19.04a	99.33b	13.98jk
AC Bog 422	17.16ab	19.04a	111.33a	17.53d-i
AC Bog 423	18.00a	14.05fg	99.33b	15.93h-j
AC Bog 424	14.00f-i	16.87cd	110.33a	18.70b-g
AC Bog 425	16.33a-f	19.02a	99.33b	13.61jk
AC Bog 426	16.33a-f	18.66ab	112.33a	19.42b-f
AC Bog 427	14.50e-h	12.36h	98.66b	17.95d-i
AC Bog 428	14.00f-i	16.16cd	110.66a	20.51bc
AC Bog 429	14.00f-i	19.58a	103.00a	18.64b-g
AC Bog 430	13.50g-i	19.69a	99.33b	19.39b-f
AC Bog 431	16.90a-d	19.88a	99.33b	12.51k
AC Bog 433	13.00g-j	18.66ab	114.00a	17.12e-i
AC Bog 434	10.33k	16.47cd	98.66b	16.92g-i
AC Bog 435	17.00a-c	16.88cd	108.55a	18.65b-g
BARI Piaz-1	18.00a	17.32bc	107.66a	14.69ij
BARI Piaz-4	14.59d-h	15.66de	108.33a	19.97b-d
CV (%)	9.81	5.87	4.80	9.02
Level of sig.	**	**	*	**

** Significant at 1% level of probability and * Significant at 5% level of probability

Disease and thrips infestation

The findings exhibited significant difference on the incidence of disease due to germplasm/varieties (Fig. 3). The disease incidence ranged from 50.00 to 13.66%. The maximum disease incidence score of purple blotch was observed in the genotype AC Bog 419 inconsistently followed by AC Bog 417 (49.66%), BARI Piaz-1 (47.85%) but consistently followed by BARI Piaz-4 (46.90%), AC Bog 435 (46.77%). The minimum incidence rating was exhibited in the genotype AC Bog 413 (13.66%). The present evaluation revealed that no genotype/variety was recorded in the disease severity category 0, 1 and 5 under 0-5 scale (Sharma, 1986). Among the 27 germplasm/varieties, thirteen germplasm (AC Bog 411, AC Bog 416, AC Bog 417, AC Bog 419, AC Bog 421, AC Bog 424, AC Bog 425, AC Bog 427, AC Bog 429, AC Bog 433, AC Bog 435, BARI Piaz-1 and BARI Piaz-4) were remained under the disease intensity category 4 and eleven genotypes were in the category 3 (AC Bog 409, AC Bog 410, AC Bog 412, AC Bog 414, AC Bog 415, AC Bog 420, AC Bog 422, AC Bog 423, AC Bog 426, AC Bog 428 and AC Bog 434). However, only three landraces- AC Bog 413, AC Bog 430 and AC Bog 431 matched with the category 2. The apparent cause of the variation in disease severity among the landraces/varieties might have been due to their genetic potential.

Similarly, considerable variation also occurred in the thrips infestation among genotypes/variety, presented in the Figure 4. The thrips severity rating ranged from 93.28 to 50.22%. The highest thrips infestation was occurred in the genotype AC Bog 416 negligibly followed by AC Bog 420 90.00%), AC Bog 414 (88.66%) and significantly followed by AC Bog 434 (83.56%), BARI Piaz-1 (83.33%), AC Bog 428 (30.30%), AC Bog 435 (83.23%) and BARI Piaz-4 (76.68%). The lowest score (50.22 & 50.58%) was detected in the AC Bog 431 and AC Bog 421, respectively. As well, the thrips severity score was 66.66% for both of the genotypes-AC Bog 413 and AC Bog 430. Similarly, the fluctuation in thrips infestation among the genotypes/variety might happen due to similar causes as found for the disease infestation. The similar results have also been reported by Thingalmaniyan *et al.* (2017) [23].

Days to maturity

The data depicted that genotypes/varieties varied widely in days to maturity of bulbs (Table 2). The days to maturity ranged from 114.00 to 98.66 days. The AC Bog 433 took 114.00 days for maturing the bulbs inconsistently followed by the genotypes- AC Bog 410 (113.33 days), AC Bog 411 (112.40 days), AC Bog 426 (112.33 days), AC Bog 422 (111.33 days), AC Bog 428 (110.66 days) and AC Bog 424 (110.33 days). On the other hand, the minimum days to mature (98.66 days) were required for two genotypes- AC Bog 427 and AC Bog 434 followed (99.33 days) by the five genotypes: AC Bog 421, AC Bog 423, AC Bog 425, AC Bog 430 and AC Bog 431. The varieties- BARI Piaz-1 and BARI Piaz-4 needed 107.66 and 108.33 days to maturity, respectively which were not consistent with days to maturity of maximum yielding genotype AC Bog 413 (103.33 days). The difference in maturity of bulbs could be due to genetic character among genotypes/varieties. The result is in accordance with the earlier report of Walle *et al.* (2018) [10], Arya *et al.* (2017) [20] and Lancaster *et al.* (1995) [22].

Diameter of bulb

A significant variation in diameter of bulb was found among landraces/varieties, shown in the Table 2. The genotype AC Bog 413 had the biggest diameter of bulb (4.98 cm) which was significantly followed by the genotypes-AC Bog 415 (4.25 cm), AC Bog 428 (4.13 cm) and AC Bog 409 (4.10 cm). Moreover, the AC Bog 431 showed the smallest one (3.26 cm). The varieties- BARI Piaz-1 and BARI Piaz-4 yielded 3.53 cm & 4.09 cm of mean bulb diameter, respectively. The finding of the current experiment might also happen due to genetic differences among the genotypes/varieties screened. The result concurs with that of Arya *et al.* (2017) [20] and Walle *et al.* (2018) [10].

Bulb weight

There were significant differences in bulb weight among accessions/varieties (Table 2). The heaviest individual bulb (36.76 g) was noted from genotype AC Bog 413 followed by AC Bog 415 (30.44 g), AC Bog 420 (30.23 g), BARI Piaz-4 (29.99 g) and AC Bog 416 (29.95 g). The lightest individual bulb (18.80 g) was observed in AC Bog 431. In addition, the BARI Piaz-1 gave rise to 22.10 g of mean individual bulb. The maximum weight of bulb produced by AC Bog 413 was 66.33 and 22.57% higher than that of BARI Piaz-1 and BARI Piaz-4, respectively. The difference in bulb weight could be attributed due to genetic potential of the germplasm/varieties. The outcome of the current study confirms the previous findings of Sirajo and Namu (2019) [16].

Multiplier bulbs

The Figure 5 demonstrated that the germplasm/varieties were found to be rich in variability on the percent of multiplier bulbs. The maximum multiplier bulb (19.25%) was recorded from AC Bog 435 significantly followed by AC Bog 426

(15.66%), BARI Piaz-1 (13.22%) and BARI Piaz-4 (12.90). However, the minimum split bulb was counted from the genotypes-AC Bog 413 (0.22%) and AC Bog 429 (0.24%). The genotype AC Bog 413 gave 98.33 and 98.29% lower multiplier bulb than that of BARI Piaz-1 and BARI Piaz-4, respectively. The variation in multiplier bulb was mainly attributed to the genetic effect of genotypes/varieties. The similar claims were also made by Arya *et al.* (2017) [20].

Dry matter content of bulbs

A considerable variation was observed in the bulb dry matter content (DMC) of onion genotypes/varieties (Table 2). The maximum DMC (19.88%) was obtained from the AC Bog 431 insignificantly followed by the accessions AC Bog 430 (19.69%), AC Bog 429 (19.58%) and AC Bog 415 (19.16%). However, the minimum DMC was noted in the AC Bog 419 (10.66%). The recommended varieties-BARI Piaz-1 and BARI Piaz-4 registered 17.32% and 15.66% of DMC, respectively. Furthermore, the AC bog 413 had the DMC of 15.53%. The variation in the DMC might have due to characteristic derived genetically from ancestor. These results agree with those of Arya *et al.* (2017) [20] who reported that genotypes/varieties significantly influenced the percent dry matter of bulbs. The DMC has been reported to contribute largely to the firmness of bulb, as noted by Sirajo and Namu (2019) [16]. The DMC is also believed to influence long storage period in onion (Mahanthesh *et al.*, 2008) [24].

Total soluble solid content

Statistically significant difference was noted in the total soluble solids (TSS) content among the genotypes/varieties, exhibited in the Table 2. The topmost TSS content (18.00 °brix) was simultaneously obtained from one genotype (AC Bog 423) and one variety (BARI Piaz-1) inconsistently followed by AC Bog 422 (17.16 °brix) and AC Bog 435 (17.00 °brix). The least TSS content (10.33 & 11.00 °brix) was observed from AC Bog 434 and AC Bog 412, respectively. Anyway, the TSS reading (14.59 & 14.50 °brix) was recorded from BARI Piaz-4 and AC Bog 413, respectively. The variation in TSS content among the genotypes/varieties might have been due to their inherent characteristics. The similar variability in TSS content among the genotypes was also registered by Arya *et al.* (2017) [20].

Yield

The genotypes/varieties had significant variation in yield per hectare, presented in the Table 2. The AC Bog 413 produced the maximum yield of 25.37 t/ha which was superior over the check varieties-BARI Piaz-1 (14.69 t/ha) and BARI Piaz-4 (19.97 t/ha). The maximum yield was significantly followed by the AC Bog 415 (21.17 t/ha), AC Bog 428 (20.51 t/ha) and AC Bog 409 (20.09 t/ha). The lowest was (12.51 t/ha) in AC Bog 431. In addition, the genotypes-AC Bog 413 produced higher yield of bulbs than that of BARI Piaz-1 and BARI Piaz-4, as being 72.70 and 27.04%, respectively. The superior performance over the check varieties/remaining genotypes could be due to their higher individual bulb weight along with their inherited wealth. The similar result was also provided by Walle *et al.* (2018) [10], Dwivedi *et al.* (2012) [25] and Lancaster *et al.* (1995) [22].

Shape index and shape of bulbs

The data in the Table 3 stated that a marked variation was recorded in shape index of bulb for different accessions/varieties. The highest shape index (1.30) was attained in the BARI Piaz-4 followed by the genotypes/variety AC Bog 409 (1.28), AC bog 413 (1.08) and BARI Piaz-1 (1.00) but the AC Bog 424 showed the lowest shape index (0.71). It is speculated that the shape index might be genetically attributed in the genotypes/varieties. These results are in harmony with the findings of Sirajo and Namu (2019), Arya *et al.* (2017) and Grant and Carter (1991) as they recorded a considerable variation in the bulb shape index of onion genotypes [16] [20] [26]. Three shapes of onion bulb were exhibited in the 27 germplasm/varieties. The BARI Piaz-4, the genotypes- AC Bog 409 and AC Bog 413 all had torpedo shapes while the BARI Piaz-1 had globular shape. The remaining twenty three genotypes got flat shape. Similar observation was also made by Sirajo and Namu (2019). The bulb shape an important marketing attribute, is genotypically influenced (Sirajo and Namu, 2019) [16].

Bulb firmness

The result from subjective method of firmness detection indicated that the firmness of bulbs was notably influenced by genotypes/varieties (Table 3). The variety BARI Piaz-1 and seven accessions (AC Bog 413, AC Bog 421, AC Bog 422, AC Bog 425, AC Bog 426, AC Bog 430 & AC Bog 431) concurrently scored the highest firmness value (9.00). The highest firmness value was markedly followed by the firmness score (8.25) of BARI Piaz-4 and AC Bog 435, Moreover, the lowest firmness rating (6.00) was observed unitedly in the landraces-AC Bog 409, AC Bog 419 and AC Bog 433. The probable cause for firmness variation might be due to difference of genetic nature among the genotypes/varieties studied. The present result is in line with that of Larsen *et al.* (2009) [27]. In addition, the strength of bulb firmness is important to store onions for long period.

Skin and flesh colour of bulb

The result of colour measurement revealed that there was variation among the 27 germplasm/varieties on skin and flesh colour of bulb (Table 3). Different skin colour of bulb was found under the trial like bronze red, pink red, red and light red. Among 27 genotypes/varieties, one variety and nine genotypes expressed bronze red namely BARI Piaz-1, AC Bog 421, AC Bog 422, AC Bog 423, AC Bog 425, AC Bog 426, AC Bog 429, AC Bog 430 and AC Bog 431. The eleven genotypes- AC Bog 409, AC Bog 411, AC Bog 412, AC Bog 414, AC Bog 415, AC Bog 416, AC Bog 420, AC Bog 428, AC Bog 433, AC Bog 434 and AC Bog 435 exposed light red colour. Five genotypes- AC Bog 410, AC Bog 413, AC Bog 417, AC Bog 424 and AC Bog 427 had pink red in colour. Moreover, red colour was exhibited by BARI Piaz-4 and AC Bog 419.

Table 3. Shape index value, shape, firmness, colour of bulb and storage loss of onion as influenced by onion accession lines/varieties at SRSC, BARI, Faridpur during 2019-2020

Accession lines/varieties	Shape index of bulb		Shape of bulb	Firmness (0-9 scale)	Colour of bulb	
	Values	Types of index			Skin	Flesh
AC Bog 409	1.28a	>1	Torpedo	6.00f	Light red	Reddish
AC Bog 410	0.73m-o	<1	Flat	6.75e	Pink red	Reddish
AC Bog 411	0.82g-j	<1	Flat	7.00de	Light red	Reddish
AC Bog 412	0.74l-o	<1	Flat	8.00bc	Light red	Reddish
AC Bog 413	1.08b	>1	Torpedo	9.00a	Pink red	Reddish
AC Bog 414	0.73m-o	<1	Flat	6.50ef	Light red	Reddish
AC Bog 415	0.98c	<1	Flat	6.50ef	Light red	Reddish
AC Bog 416	0.81g-k	<1	Flat	6.50ef	Light red	Reddish
AC Bog 417	0.80h-l	<1	Flat	6.75e	Pink red	Reddish
AC Bog 419	0.79h-m	<1	Flat	6.00f	Red	Pale reddish
AC Bog 420	0.72no	<1	Flat	6.50ef	Light red	Reddish
AC Bog 421	0.82g-j	<1	Flat	9.00a	Bronze red	Pale reddish
AC Bog 422	0.83g-i	<1	Flat	9.00a	Bronze red	White
AC Bog 423	0.93de	<1	Flat	8.00bc	Bronze red	Pale reddish
AC Bog 424	0.71o	<1	Flat	8.00bc	Pink red	Reddish
AC Bog 425	0.82g-j	<1	Flat	9.00a	Bronze red	White
AC Bog 426	0.87e-g	<1	Flat	9.00a	Bronze red	White
AC Bog 427	0.75k-o	<1	Flat	8.00bc	Pink red	Reddish
AC Bog 428	0.76j-o	<1	Flat	7.50cd	Light red	Pale reddish
AC Bog 429	0.77i-o	<1	Flat	6.75e	Bronze red	Reddish
AC Bog 430	0.80h-l	<1	Flat	9.00a	Bronze red	White
AC Bog 431	0.75k-o	<1	Flat	9.00a	Bronze red	Reddish
AC Bog 433	0.85f-h	<1	Flat	6.00f	Light red	Pale reddish
AC Bog 434	0.78i-n	<1	Flat	8.00bc	Light red	Reddish
AC Bog 435	0.91ef	<1	Flat	8.25b	Light red	White
BARI Piaz-1	0.85f-h	<1	Flat	9.00a	Bronze red	White
BARI Piaz-4	1.30a	>1	Torpedo	8.25b	Red	White
CV (%)	10.52	-	-	5.84	-	-
Level of sig.	**	-	-	**	-	-

** Significant at 1% level of probability

The flesh colour of bulb was reddish in fifteen genotypes: AC Bog 409, AC Bog 410, AC Bog 411, AC Bog 412, AC Bog 413, AC Bog 414, AC Bog 415, AC Bog 416, AC Bog 417, AC Bog 420, AC Bog 424, AC Bog 427, AC Bog 429, AC Bog 431 and AC Bog 434. Pale reddish flesh colour of bulb was detected in five germplasm such as AC Bog 419, AC Bog 421, AC Bog 428 and AC Bog 433. Nonetheless, the remaining genotypes- AC Bog 422, AC Bog 425, AC Bog 426, AC Bog 430, AC Bog 435 and two varieties-BARI Piaz-1 and BARI Piaz-4 demonstrated white flesh colour in bulb. The recorded variation in colour of bulb among the genotypes/varieties might be due to their differences in genetic makeup. Similarly,

Ratan *et al.* (2017) and Lancaster *et al.* (1995) also published significant variation among the genotypes for colour of bulb [7] [22].

Pungency

The finding of organoleptic taste stated that the pungency of onion responded distinctly due to genotypes/varieties studied, illustrated in the Figure 6. Flavour perception score for pungency ranged from 5.00 to 1.00. The strongest pungency (5.00) was simultaneously recorded in BARI Piaz-1 and AC Bog 417 which was insignificantly followed by AC Bog 421 (4.50) and AC Bog 431 (4.50). The variety BARI Piaz-4 and the six genotypes of AC Bog 413, AC Bog 419, AC Bog 423, AC Bog 425, AC Bog 429 and AC Bog 435 had the pungency level of 4.00 which was distinctly varied with the highest pungency score. In addition, three genotypes namely AC Bog 409, AC Bog 410 and AC Bog 416 scored the lowest pungency level (1.00) which level was mainly sweet in organoleptic taste. The variation in pungency of onion among the genotypes/varieties might be due to their genetic potential. Wall and Corgan (1992) found wide variation in pungency among the genotypes by flavour perception method[14].

Fig. 6. Flavour perception for pungency as per genotypes/varieties. The vertical bar represents the LSD at 5% level of probability.

Shelf life of onion

The genotypes/varieties posed significant responses on the shelf life of onion (Fig. 7). The loss of onion in the store ranged from 90.02 to 29.94%. The minimum weight loss (29.94%) was observed from AC Bog 413 significantly followed by BARI Biaz-1 (35.53%), AC Bog 435 (36.09%), BARI Piaz-4 (37.38%) and AC Bog 430 (39.40%). However, the maximum weight loss (90.02%) was recorded in AC Bog 414 insignificantly followed by AC Bog 409 (86.73%) and AC Bog 415 (86.66%). The difference in storage potentiality among the genotypes could be due to the similar cause as quoted above in case of pungency. The finding is in line with the finding of Isma'ila *et al.* (2017) who found significant variation among the varieties[28].

Fig. 7. Storage loss of onion as per genotypes/varieties. The Vertical bar represents the LSD at 5% level of probability.

Conclusion

Based on the outcomes of the present study, it could be concluded as follows:

- The genotype AC Bog 413 exhibited superior performance in incidence of bolting (2.36%), disease severity (13.66%), bulb diameter (BD-4.98 cm), individual bulb weight (IBW-36.76 g), multiplier bulb (0.22%), days to maturity (103.33 days) and yield (25.37 t/ha) over the recommended varieties-BARI Piaz-1 and BARI Piaz-4.
- The AC Bog 413 gave 66.33 & 22.57% higher individual bulb weight, 72.70 & 27.04% higher bulb yield, 98.33 & 98.29% lower split bulb and 90.74 & 91.03% lower pre-mature bolting than those of BARI Piaz-1 and BARI Piaz-4, respectively.
- However, the BARI Piaz-1 had higher dry matter content (17.32%), higher TSS content (18.00 °brix) and stronger pungency (5.00) than those of AC Bog 413 (15.53%, 14.50 °brix, & 4.00), respectively.
- Simultaneously BARI Piaz-1 and AC Bog 413 showed firmer bulbs (9.00) than that of BARI Piaz-4 (8.25).
- The AC Bog 413 had the lowest storage loss (29.94%) among the genotypes/varieties followed by BARI Piaz-1 (35.53%) and BARI Piaz-4 (37.38%).
- The skin and flesh colour of bulbs were identified as bronze red & white for BARI Piaz-1; red & white for BARI Piaz-4 and pink red & reddish for AC Bog 413, respectively.
- The variety BARI Piaz-4 and AC Bog 413 exhibited torpedo shape of bulb while BARI Piaz-1 showed flat shape of bulb.

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